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Science Camp - Science first hand at BME

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ABSTRACT

The STEM education is facing considerable global challenges. The gap between education and research keeps growing because of the rapid expansion of knowledge generated by scientific research. Smart products or services of nowadays are based on scientific achievements but can be used with decreasing knowledge. Preserving secondary school students with scientific or engineering interest on these fields is a challenge. Consequently firsthand knowledge acquisition and experience-based learning are getting more and more valued.

The aim of our camp is to show the amazing colorfulness of physics and mathematics and their connections to other fields.

Another objective is to familiarize the children with the way the university function and – through the involvement of the students of Budapest University of Technology and Economics (BME) - the everyday student life. BME students play a key role in transmitting knowledge. On the other hand, they have an opportunity to taste social responsibility.

We target students who are at the point of deciding on their future career. We put special emphasis to select groups who are currently under-represented in our study programs. During our scientific programs we pick and show them topics that are

currently not covered by the high school curriculum but are supposed to be essential throughout their career.

During the week students participate in lectures; work on exercises from different fields and visit technology intensive external sites.

We plan to present the experiences and feed-backs collected during the four editions of Science Camp.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, many studies have reported an alarming decline in young people's interest for STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) subjects [1,2]. It is highly desired to reverse this trend since the lack of STEM-skilled labour would be one of the main obstacles for economic growth. Besides the increase of the number of youngsters choosing engineering and natural sciences for their higher education, improving STEM-skills of those, who already hold a degree, is also necessary. In fact, the main contemporary challenge for the higher education is not to select the best students among the many good applicants but to find enough students worth for admission.

Some reasons of the low attractiveness of STEM studies are as follows:

- Students often lack real information on STEM professions and careers, e.g. how they look like in the real-life. As this field is rapidly evolving, often even the teachers and the career orientation counsellors do not have enough up-to-date information to help the students choose.
- Often the curriculum does not keep up with the latest scientific achievements thus its relevance is unclear for the students: they do not see the relation between the curriculum and the current issues of society.
- Experiments and team work are missing, although they could harness such experiences in real-life situations.
- Education does not go further than the institutional limits, i.e. the amount of field practice, industrial internship possibilities are limited.

All over Europe, women are underrepresented among those who choose STEM education [3,4]. In Hungary, growing expatriation of skilled high school students is a considerable issue. Actually more than 13,000 Hungarian students are learning abroad [5]. It is also a challenge to keep those high school students who take interest in STEM on a continued track.

Consequently, according to our conviction, first-hand knowledge acquisition and experience-based learning are becoming more and more invaluable. To mention a few examples, it can inspire tenacity and motivate to humble and hard work to see how 50 % of the overall Hungarian energy consumption is generated in a few power plant halls, or to visit the cutting-edge production site of a company (Semilab), which is a successful actor of the international semiconductor industry. Another example is

to visit the National Institute of Oncology, where bio-medical imaging instruments are used extensively, all which are the result of the STEM related developments in the past 20 years [5].

Another paradox of our age is that the extent of the knowledge base required for a successful career is expanding. Lifelong learning and training are no longer an attractive notion but it has become a daily requirement for industry professionals. Nevertheless, it is becoming increasingly difficult to maintain the attention of young people during knowledge transfer. A common and widespread surmise is that any information can be easily reached from the internet on the smartphone so conventional learning is of limited benefit. To mention a real-world example, when someone is interested in nuclear energy or financial mathematics, browsing Wikipedia in 10 minutes (s)he can absorb more knowledge than the average. However this superficial knowledge will leave just as fast as it came. Moreover, no links with other fields are created so it cannot become a deep, practically usable knowledge.

In many cases, Hungarian youngsters living in the countryside or abroad are apprehensive of living in a metropolis and do not dare to choose the institutions of the capital. In order to overcome these difficulties, our faculty launched the “Science Camp” summer camp focusing on natural sciences in 2016. During the one week long camp, free accommodation and full board is granted for all attending high school students.

Though summer schools for high school students are organised all over the world [6,7] but the concept and the financial conditions of the Science Camp are very different.

2. The summer school

2. 1. The aim of the camp

The objective of the camp is to show the amazing colourfulness of physics and mathematics and to give an idea about their connections to other fields (medicine, chemistry, IT, engineering, and economics). Another goal was to familiarize the students with the way of operation of the university and – through the involvement of BME students the everyday student life. We also aim to motivate students for open-minded thinking and innovation, to improve their financial and legal skills. Throughout the social and cultural activities and sport programs, we also promote the BME and the local environment, the XIth District of Budapest. We hope that these efforts could contribute to the choice of BME at first place, overtaking even foreign institutions, when these students decide about the continuation of their studies.

2.2. Target audience

The target group for the camp is composed of 10th or 11th grade high school students who are at the point of deciding on their future education. We put special emphasis to select groups who are currently under-represented in our study programs (e.g. girls, students coming from the countryside, less-favoured regions, and from the Hungarian speaking minorities outside Hungary). Following a comprehensive information campaign about our camp in numerous high schools, students were selected for admission based on the recommendation letter of their teachers and a letter of motivation. A 4 membered scientific jury, which represents physicists, mathematics, and the student organization, evaluates the applicants and selects the participants of the camp. We pay special attention to give the opportunity for as many applicants living in economically less developed regions or abroad (mainly students of Hungarian mother tongue living in the neighbour countries) as possible. It is much more difficult for this target group to get into or even to acquire information about an event organised in Budapest than for those who live in Budapest or in its agglomeration. As the camp is funded by social sponsors or companies, their donation contributes directly to the advance of these young people. The distribution of the applicants by region is shown in *Fig. 1*. The circle diameters are proportional to the number of accepted students.

Fig. 1. The distribution of the applicants by region (2016).

We consider that the summer camp is successful if we can achieve that majority of our students choose a higher education, which focuses on natural sciences or engineering in Hungary.

2.3. Programs

During our scientific programs, we try to select and present them topics that are currently not covered by the high school curriculum but are supposed to be essential throughout their future career.

During the one-week long camp, students participate in scientific lectures, they work in teams on competition exercises from different fields (e.g. mathematics, physics, nuclear or medical physics, and financial mathematics). Thanks to the rich network of partnerships of the BME and the multifaceted experience on the labour market of our graduated former students, the high school students have the opportunity to visit technology intensive external sites (*Table 2.a*). With these external visits we wish to go beyond the traditional framework of the scholar education by showing real-life experiences, stories, and role models for the students. *Fig. 2*.

Fig. 2. Visit to Paks Nuclear Power Plant in 2018

Another important field, where we pay special attention to overcome the limitations of traditional education, is that we put great emphasis on solving problems together, in team. In contrast to the scholar education, where mostly the individual achievements are measured and evaluated, we encourage and promote teamwork. We believe that most of the scientific, financial or technological success stories are the results of coordinated teamwork. In a team, members having diversified skills and different personalities can complete each other and create results and solutions that go beyond their individual competence. To demonstrate the force of teamwork to the participants, we provide problems to the students to solve in small teams.

Fig. 3. Teamwork

As a result of our methodology of student selection, all pupils are highly-skilled and open-minded but their social background is very different just as their personalities, e.g. their self-confidence. Besides intellectual and cultural challenges, various social activities and sport programs play an important role in the program.

The most important programs of the camp of 2018 are summarised in *Tables 1-3*.

Table 1. Lectures

Lectures
From Fibonacci numbers to shift register
How reliable are numerical computations on computers?
Topological curiosities
Small evening physics

Table 2. Visits

a.) External visits
Paks Nuclear Power Plant. The Information and Visitors Centre and the Museum of Nuclear Energetics
Morgan Stanley
Centre for Budapest Transport: Central Traffic Management, Courier Center / Industry 4.0 (BME)
SEMILAB (semiconductor industry) / Oncological Institute
b.) BME Laboratories
Institute of Nuclear Techniques: training reactor, medical physics, plasma physics of fusion
Institute of Physics: nanoelectronics, high field electron spin resonance, molecular electronics magneto-optical

Table 3. Other programs

Other programs	Leisure time programs
Team-work problem solving	Sport, Sport Center BME
Competition	Escape Game (BME, HSZI)
Meeting with alumni	Get together party
Creative writing	Boat trip on the Danube
BME promenade with the eye of an architect	Closing Ceremony
	Gellért Hill

2.4. University student participants

From the very first moment, we paid great importance to the university students who helped in the realization of the dense programs located on multiple sites. They were mostly BSc and MSc students in physics, chemical engineering, and mathematics. They actively participate in guiding the students between sites, in the realization of the social events and competitions, and they help them adapt to the life in the

college. There are 20-21 university students who participate in each summer camp. This may seem excessive compared to the number of student participants (between 45 and 60). However according to our experience, university students can be considered as rather active participants as compared to the persons who help in the arrangement and organisation of the camp. As an added benefit, the scientific programs have also a significant impact on the vision of the university students about natural sciences and their devotion to the speciality chosen. They play an important role in knowledge transfer through informal discussions with high school student. This also gives the university students a possibility to participate in social responsibility programmes as well.

3. Feed-back

From 2016, altogether 231 students participated in the four Science Camps. From the 135 students who graduated from high school , and could apply to higher education, 67 were admitted to one of the faculties at BME. It clearly satisfies the , above set criterion, which we consider as success for the camp.

On the last day of the camp, both high school and university students respond to an anonymous satisfaction survey. The results were always delighting to the organizers of the camp. The high school students gave high scores for both the overall camp and the participation and support of university students. Lots of useful observations are made which we try to consider in the following edition of the camp. Nevertheless, the different focus of interest and social background of the children is also reflected in their comments and observations.

3.1. Selective examples

-What do you recommend for the next Science camp?

A common suggestion was to make the timetable a little bit less crowded, leave more leisure time and to organize more sport program. Somebody wrote: “Maybe the schedule was crowded but so we had insight to more things”.

- Do the things that you saw and heard in the camp influence your occupational choice?

In many cases, according to the responses the things experienced and heard in the camp helped or influenced (strengthened) the choice. That is, these students would choose more confidently the BME after the camp than before. E.g.: 1. ‘I got a positive feedback on BME about which I had scarce information before. Now I have a more complete picture of it.’ 2. “The camp showed me and made me consider new options which were unknown to me before”. 3. “No, but my choice of the BME university overtakes all other options.”

In some cases, the camp aroused the interest for the study programs of the Faculty of Natural Sciences. 1. “I saw that physics is better and less boring than I had

thought before.” 2. “I got convinced that the physics formation is not exclusively about physics. I saw that finding a job will be possible in several different fields. I feel like going to a college.” 3. I got to know that physicists can work elsewhere than in research, this helps me choose the formation of physics”. 4. Honestly, I took into consideration to choose physics and the Faculty of Natural Sciences, however I had been thinking about completely different directions before.” 5. “Yes, I think the camp made me even more confused. I do not really know yet. But the spectrum became larger from what I can choose”.

In some cases who replied yes, it was impossible to clearly identify what they were thinking about. E.g.: 1. “Yes, the camp confirmed that the profession I plan is nice and interesting.” 2. “Yes, the presented formations attract me even more than before”. 3. Yes, we heard honest opinion about the university, its faculties and about the life here.” 4. “Yes. It was efficiently demonstrated what kind of work is to be done during an engineer or physicist career. Moreover we could participate in such programs and experiments. I see now more clearly the similarities and the differences. This will help me in choosing my career which is actual soon.”

These citations illustrate that the camp made deep professional and/or human impression on the students. We consider that our goal to show them alternatives for their career choice was reached.

Fig. 4. After the closing ceremony (2019.)

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